

V KONGRES
SRPSKE
ORTOPEDSKO
TRAUMATOLOŠKE
ASOCIJACIJE

BEOGRAD, 13 – 15. oktobar 2016.

SOTA

SRPSKA ORTOPEDSKO TRAUMATOLOŠKA ASOCIJACIJA
SERBIAN ORTHOPAEDIC TRAUMA ASSOCIATION

ZBORNİK SAŽETAKA
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

BELGRADE, 13 – 15 October 2016

**5th CONGRESS OF THE
SERBIAN
ORTHOPAEDIC
TRAUMA
ASSOCIATION**

Poštovane kolegice i kolege, dragi prijatelji velika mi je čast i zadovoljstvo da Vas u ime Srpske Ortopedsko Traumatološke Asocijacije (SOTA) pozovem na Peti Kongres SOTA-e koji se održava od 13. do 15. oktobra 2016. godine u Beogradu.

Od osnivanja našeg udruženja juna 2007. godine, bili smo domaćini četiri izuzetno uspešna kongresa. Organizacija petog Kongresa SOTA-e u ovim teškim vremenima još jednom ističe potrebu za postojanjem udruženja ortopedskih hirurga i traumatologa Srbije.

Ovaj kongres je rezultat dugotrajnog napornog rada i naše želje da nas okupi i usmeri ka zajedničkom cilju – uspešnijem lečenju naših pacijenata.

Nadamo se da će ovaj kongres sa međunarodnim učešćem pružiti priliku za nesebičnu razmenu i širenje novih iskustava i znanja, kreativnu diskusiju i uspostavljanje novih prijateljstava.

Kao Predsednik Srpske Ortopedsko Traumatološke Asocijacije imam prijatnu dužnost da Vam srdačno poželim dobrodošlicu na V Kongres SOTA-e, uspešan rad, puno novih poznanstava i lepog druženja u predivnom Beogradu.

Dear colleagues, dear friends, it is my great honor and pleasure to invite you on behalf of the Serbian Orthopaedic Trauma Association (SOTA) to the Fifth SOTA Congress to be held between 13 and 15 October 2016 in Belgrade.

Since the founding of our organization in June 2007, we hosted four very successful congresses. Organizing the fifth SOTA Congress in these difficult times reiterates the need for an association of orthopaedic surgeons and traumatologists of Serbia.

This congress is a result of a long and hard work and our desire to bring us together and steer us towards the common goal – a more successful treatment of our patients. We hope this congress with international participation will provide an opportunity for the selfless sharing and dissemination of new knowledge and experience, creative discussion and new friendships.

As President of the Serbian Orthopaedic Trauma Association, I have a pleasant duty to warmly welcome you to the 5th SOTA Congress and wish you success in future work, plenty of new contacts and enjoyable socializing in the beautiful Belgrade.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Marko Bumbaširević'. The signature is fluid and cursive.

Predsednik V kongresa SOTA 2016 i predsednik SOTA
President of the 5th SOTA Congress 2016 and President of SOTA
prof dr / Prof. MD Marko Bumbaširević

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V KONGRES SRPSKE ORTOPEDSKO
TRAUMATOLOŠKE ASOCIJACIJE
BEOGRAD, 13 – 15. OKTOBAR 2016

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5TH CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN
ORTHOPAEDIC TRAUMA ASSOCIATION
BELGRADE, 2 – 4 OCTOBER 2014

Pokrovitelj Kongresa / Under the Auspices of the

Ministarstvo zdravlja Republike Srbije
Ministry of Health of Republic of Serbia

Organizator Kongresa / Congress Organiser

SOTA – Srpska ortopedsko traumatološka asocijacija
SOTA – Serbian Orthopaedic Trauma Association

Predsednik SOTA / President of SOTA

prof dr Marko Bumbaširević

Predsednik Kongresa / President of Congress

prof dr Marko Bumbaširević

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PLEXUS BRACHIALIS BLOCK IN SHOULDER JOINT SURGERY INTERSCALENE APPROACH

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Introduction: The shoulder joint is the mobile joint of the human body and also very prone to injuries (tendon and ligament strains, sprains, strains or tendon rupture). Some sports activities often lead to injuries of the shoulder joint, which, in some cases, can lead to permanent impairment of the function and stopping career in sports.

In recent decades, the rapid development of minimally invasive surgical techniques (arthroscopy) and the development of modern drugs and anesthetic techniques provide a better postoperative recovery and a faster return to daily activities and sport activities.

Figure 1. Plexus brachialis

There are several techniques for blocking plexus brachialis (fig.1). In our everyday clinical practice, we perform the interscalene approach, which gives good anaesthesia for the brachial and cervical plexus too. The interscalene approach to brachial plexus gives good regional anesthesia and analgesia for feasible surgical procedures on the upper extremity and shoulder.

Objectives:

- Ability to perform surgical procedures of the shoulder and upper arm,

- Avoiding complications associated with general anesthesia
- Muscle relaxation for the surgeon
- Postoperative analgesia
- Better postoperative recovery

Technique: The upper, middle and lower trunks of the brachial plexus are found between the anterior and middle scalene muscles. This is called the interscalene groove. The interscalene groove is found at the level of the cricoid cartilage. The external jugular vein will cross the area of the interscalene groove at the level of the cricoid cartilage. A common mistake, when first attempting this approach, is to confuse the groove between the sternocleidomastoid and anterior scalene muscle. This groove is anterior to the interscalene groove (fig.2- interscalene groove).

Once the correct area is identified, a total of 30-40 ml of local anesthetic is injected. Frequent aspiration should occur during injection, ensuring an intravenous injection does not occur. Do not inject if the patient experiences pain or it is difficult to inject the local anesthetic. Digital pressure, applied proximally, may help with distal spread of the local anesthetic (fig.3).

Lidocaine, Ropivacaine and Bupivacaine are commonly administered for the interscalene approach. Bupivacaine and Ropivacaine will have an onset of 20-30 minutes, an anesthetic duration of 8-10 hours, and provide analgesia for 16-18 hours.

Complications: Pneumothorax, block n. phrenicus, n. recurrens, n.vagus are the complications that can occur with the interscalene approach. Plexus brachialis is avoided.

Figure 2. Plexus brachialis block - interscalene approach

Conclusions: The application of modern local anesthetics and peripheral nerve blockade, combined with the minimally invasive surgical technique - arthroscopy, significantly contribute to the rapid and comfortable postoperative recovery.

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NEOPERATIVNI PRISTUP LEČENJU PRELOMA TALUSA, PRIKAZ SLUČAJA / UNOPERATIVE TREATMENT OF TALAR FRACTURES, CASE REPORT

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Sažetak: Iako čine svega do 3% svih preloma skočnog zgloba, talarne fracture su bitne jer su zbog anatomskih specifičnosti teške za lečenje i često se komplikuju trajnim invaliditetom. Poznavanje anatomije i terapijskih mogućnosti operativnog i neoperativnog lečenja su ključ odluke o vrsti terapije. Dobro primenjena i sa razumnim očekivanjima daje maksimalni mogući rezultat.

Summary: Allthow they consist only up to 3% of all talocrural fractures, talar fractures matter for their specific anatomy. They are complicated to treat and end up with invalidity. Knowing anatomy and therapeutic possibility of operative and non operative treatment are key to decision about the kind of therapy we are going to use. When properly used and with reasonable expectations it gives maximum result

Definicija i podela: Talus se sastoji od tela (svod, centralni deo, lateralni i posteriorni nastavak), vrat i glava. Talus nema tetivnih pripoja, ima ligamentarnih pripoja, zglobljava se sa tibijom, laterlnim i medijalnim maleolom, petnom i navikularnom kosti. Vaskularizuje se od zadnje koje se mahom kreći uz vrat talusa.

Nešto slabija osteoblastna aktivnost i prekrivenost dve trećine kosti hrskavicom (tri zgloba: talokruralni, talonavikularni i talokalkanealni zglob), čini da je kost podložna dejstvu traume. Aksijalne i sile smicanja u okviru pojačane aktivnosti i traume, posebno u regiji tela talusa, dovode do preloma. Posebno u položaju dorzifleksije ili pri pojačanom opterećenju u položaju